

duration is too long, productivity/ d per ha declines

IR44 is a good ratooning variety, but the ratoon crop has nonsynchronous maturity and its growth duration can be more than 100 d. Nonsynchronous maturity also makes ratoon harvesting difficult.

We studied the effect of harvest time of an IR44 ratoon crop on grain yield in Dec 1983-Jul 1984 at IRRI. Twenty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 2 seedlings/hill in a 23.0- × 23.2-m² plot. NPK was applied at 120-13-25 kg/ha. Half of the N and all of P and K were incorporated at final puddling. The remaining N was topdressed at 28 and 40 d after transplanting. At maturity, five 6-m² subplots were sampled for main crop grain yield.

Plants were ratooned by cutting stalks at 15-cm height. Immediately after cutting, 40 kg N/ha was broadcast followed by insecticide spray. The ratoon crop was harvested at 75, 80, 85, and 90 d after main crop harvest (DAH). We 6-m² subplots were sampled at each harvesting date. Ten random plants from each plot were taken to record panicles/ plant, spikelets/ panicle, and spikelet fertility. Unfilled grains were separated by specific gravity method using saline solution (1.65 kg/ 10 litres of

Effect of harvest time on grain yield and components in an IR44 ratoon crop, IRRI, 1984 dry season. ^a

DAH	Panicles/ plant	Spikelets/ panicle	Spikelet fertility (%)	Fully filled grains(%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (g/m ²)	
						Actual	Adjusted
75	14 ns	61 ns	70 bc	83 b	25 ns	126 b	136 b
80	14	70	67 c	88 a	25	161 a	188 a
85	12	72	73 ab	92 a	25	168 a	196 a
90	13	67	75 a	92 a	25	151 ab	178 a

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ns = nonsignificant.

water). Grain yield at 14% moisture content was recorded and expressed in g/m².

Main crop grain yield was 516 g/m². Ratoon crop harvest time significantly affected spikelet fertility, fully filled grains, and ratoon grain yield (see table). Ratoon grain yield varied from 126 g/m² for 75 DAH to 168 g for 85 DAH. Number of regenerated hills among treatments varied from 86% for 75 DAH to 75% for 90 DAH. Ratoon grain yield was calculated based on maximum recorded regeneration (92%) to eliminate the differences due to number of regenerated hills, which caused large variations in ratoon grain yield and partially concealed the effect of time of harvest.

The lowest grain yield (136 g) was at 75 DAH and the highest at 85 DAH;

however, they were not statistically different from those at 80 and 90 DAH. Spikelet fertility did not differ significantly between 85 and 90 DAH. Spikelet fertility at 75 DAH was at par with that at 80 and 85 DAH. The differences in spikelet fertility did not explain the differences in grain yield. The proportion of fully filled grains was the lowest at 75 DAH.

The differences in fully filled and total spikelets/ panicle can explain the differences in grain yield among the treatments. Late tillers with low spikelet number/ panicle contributed to low yields in 90 DAH treatment. Shattering of overripe grains also reduced yield. The optimum time of IR44 ratoon crop harvest is 80-85 d after main crop cutting, which is still too long for most situations. *S*

Nitrogen volatilization from fertilizers applied to salt-affected coastal soils

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We studied N volatilization losses from different N fertilizers in upland and lowland salt-affected soils. Volatilized ammonia gas was trapped in a foam pad soaked with dilute sulfuric acid. The foam pad was placed 30 cm above the soil on a grill on top of a perforated cylindrical support. Volatilization was estimated using a standard curve prepared against actual losses estimated for identical field situations.

N at 100 kg/ha was applied as ammonium sulfate (AS), prilled urea

N volatilization (%)

1. Volatilization losses of N from different fertilizers, West Bengal, India. PU = prilled urea, SCU = sulfur-coated urea, LCU = lac-coated urea, UB = urea briquet, UPP = PU in paper packets, AS = ammonium sulfate.

(PU), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), lac-coated urea (LCU), urea briquet (UB) 3 g, and PU (3 g) in paper packets

(UPP) to puddled, waterlogged fields with ECe 3.5 and 7.5 mmho/cm In a pot experiment, AS and PU were applied to

soil with ECe 7.4 mmho/cm at 3 soil moisture levels: airdried, -3 bar soil water potential (20% moisture), and waterlogged. Both experiments were in three replications. Except in the first 24 h, volatilization rate was measured at 48-h intervals. Soil and floodwater pH (1:2) were 7.5 and 8.2 before fertilizer application.

Except with UB and UPP, volatilization nearly doubled at 7.5 mmho/cm (Fig. 1). Figure 2 shows that the loss from both PU and AS increased with increasing soil moisture. Volatilization was greatest during the first 3-7 d, and then gradually declined.

Results showed that N use efficiency could be improved by reducing volatilization in salt-affected lowland rice fields by applying PU instead of AS, and by placing PU 5 cm deep in soil as UPP or UB. For upland fields, fertilizer application should be timed so that soil moisture is low during and immediately following N application. *ℒ*

2. Volatilization loss of NH₃ at 3 soil moisture levels, West Bengal, India.

Response of rainfed rice to post-planting soil-management practices

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We studied the response of rainfed rice (VRS16) to 4 postemergence management practices: minimum tillage, interrow compaction at Proctor moisture content to achieve bulk densities of 1.6

and 1.8 g/cm³, embedding polythene strips in the interrow space, and conventional practices. Soil was a loamy sand with 0.44% organic C, bulk density of 1.36 g/cm³, and saturated hydraulic conductivity of 45 mm/h. Rice was sown in rows spaced at 23 cm on 6 Jul 1984. It received a basal application of 20-18-33 kg NPK/ha and topdressing of 20 kg N/ha 45 d after sowing. Treatments were imposed after complete crop emergence.

All soil modifications significantly increased grain yield as compared to the conventional practices (see table). Grain yield was highest when the interrow soil was compacted to a bulk density of 1.6 g/cm³. Embedding polythene strips between the rows also was promising. Compacting the soil to a bulk density greater than 1.6 g/cm³ reduced grain yield, possibly by restricting root proliferation. Straw yield did not differ significantly among treatments. *ℒ*

Rice grain and straw yield with different soil management practices, Almora, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	
	Grain	Straw
Minimum tillage	1.9	4.7
Compaction at Proctor moisture content to bulk density of 1.6 g/cm ³	2.0	5.1
Compaction at Proctor moisture content to bulk density of 1.8 g/cm ³	1.7	4.7
Embedding polythene strips in the interrow space	1.9	5.0
Conventional practices	1.4	4.1
CD at 5%	0.3	ns

Influence of N level and source on rice yield

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We evaluated prilled urea (PU), urea supergranules (USG), and 1% PPD urea (PPDU) in a field experiment with Co 43 at TNAU. N levels were 0, 37.5, 75.0, and 112.5 kg/ha. P, K, and Zn were applied basally at 17.6, 33.2, and 2.3 kg/ha. USG was applied at 8-10 cm depth and PU and PPDU were applied

in 3 splits. Soil was a clay (Typic Haplustalf) with pH 8.4, E.C. 0.2 mmho/cm, 107-9.8-263 ppm available NPK, 588 ppm total soil N, and 0.78% organic C.

Grain yield and crop performance were generally best with USC (see table). Plants recovered more N from USG, followed by PPDU and PU. N recovery ratio was higher at lower application rates. Postharvest soil analysis indicated that total N content did not change significantly, although USG plots had a maximum 729 ppm total N. *ℒ*